

Palynomorphological Data of Pollen Grains of *Lamium Garganicum*

Authors : Nikoleta Kallajxhiu, Gëzim Kapidani, Peçi Naqellari, Blerina Pupuleku

Abstract : This study shows palynomorphological description of pollen grains of *Lamium garganicum*, species of the family Labiatae. Fresh material of this plant is taken in Mount Llogara, in Albania. By comparison made between palinomorphic characteristics of pollen grains of *Lamium garganicum* with those of *Lamium maculatum* and *Lamium purpureum*, showed that granules have similarities in the number of furrows. The pollen grains of *Lamium garganicum* were larger in length and width than those of *Lamium maculatum* and almost equal with those of *Lamium purpureum*. Furrows are longer than those of pollen grains in *Lamium maculatum* and shorter than those of *Lamium purpureum*. The layer of exine of *Lamium garganicum* was thinner than that of two others. The sculpture of exine was fine reticulate, where reticulas were uniform whereas in *Lamium purpureum*, was verrucate, with small verrucae; in *Lamium maculatum* was reticulate.

Keywords : *Lamium garganicum*, pollen grains, Llogara, Albania.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014